

The Significance of Inter-Functional Coordination that Affect Organizational Commitment the Mediation Role of Customer Success: The case of Bule Hora General Hospital

Gada Gizachew Wakjira

Research Scholar (PhD), Collage of Business and Economics, Department of Marketing Management, Bule Hora University, Bule Hora, Ethiopia, Horn Africa.

Abstract – The purpose of this study aims the Significance of Inter-functional Coordination that Affect Organizational Commitment the Mediation Role of Customer Success: The case of Bule Hora General Hospital, Market orientation is a business perspective that makes the customer the focal point of a business company's total operation. The general objective of the study is to investigate the Significance of Inter-functional Coordination that Affect Organizational Commitment the Mediation Role of Customer Success, to seek to understand customers' expressed and latent variable it needs and develop superior solutions for those needs. The research idea stems from study findings that Inter-functional Coordination not only affects the Organizational Commitment of the concern directly but also indirectly Employee Success has also confounding to affect directly and indirectly. On the basis and types of data gathered and the instrument used, quantitative research design to use Confirmatory factor analyze and the data analysis were employed for sample size determination valid 368 respondents and as most of the respondent replied to major effect of Inter-functional Coordination data have been collected from employees the Bule Hora General Hospital and customers Customer can serve each General Hospital. The scales have been purified and validated with the help of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and the results of structure equation modeling (SEM), revealed a significant relationship

between Inter-functional Coordination and Organizational Commitment, with mediating role of Customer Success have been confirmed, which yielded to the significant results to used SPSS Version 22 and AMOS 23 to analysis SEM, Standard Regression Weights and model fit value.

Keywords: Inter-functional Coordination, Organizational Commitment and Customer Success.

1. INTRODUCTION

(Malgharn et, al., 2019), says many the scientific studies outline various approaches, to exploration of new working environment, and improved possibilities of working both on that can be motivated, and it is necessary to be familiar with the human motivational fields, the activities and processes which are related within a company and organization on the contrary, in which fields, activities and processes are independent of each other and simultaneously seen the flexibility of working environment, managers must be aware of all the external and internal factors which influence and affected the company from the surrounding environment, and all the subjects which are influenced by the company, and this knowledge can help companies in creating new strategies to launched and expand by resources, employee and customer success and these strategies must respond to all information derived from both the external and internal environments, and promptly implemented the new ideological change in

organization, and changes into the decision process, many researchers try to detect, and offer the best solution for the companies, and to help them succeed the often-mentioned approaches is inter-functional coordination.

(Swiss R., 2018), the contribution of total insurance premiums of every organization, is focused on its organizational performance thoroughly which it assures on its organizational sustainability and rapid growth change, to Measuring organizational capabilities is not clear-cut specifically for organizations with many goals, such as customer retention, organizational productivity, and organizational profitability, ability to do something to become accustomed to the ever varying environment, employee satisfaction, growth, and social responsibility for the contribution of Organization activities, and it has mostly been conceptualized on the basis of financial measures and some scholars have urged for a wider performance construct, that incorporate aspects of non-financial measures like effectiveness, employee and organizational efficiency, service quality, to change the company image, customer satisfaction, job satisfaction, and management control organizational system (Mukulu& Kahiri, 2017).

By understanding when, and how commitments develop, and how they shape attitude, and behavior, organizations will be in a better position to anticipate the impact that change will have and to manage it more effectively and by knowing what drives the commitment of employees, a positive environment, can be created to deliver tangible results quickly in each working condition to change the image of company, and the purpose of this idea, is to identify theories of the employee and Organizational commitment in the workplace to develop a framework that helps the field create higher levels of organizational commitment, organizational productivity, and customer and employee satisfaction and to manage and organized the main company sections and method, commitment of employee and customer in the

working place, mapping workplace commitment, and the implications for Human Resource, (Altinay Dart & Aglonye M., 2016).

To address this inquiry, background literature and prior research is explored, followed by the development of a formal hypothetical model, which explains, in the context of generate research based development each organization by of new idea generation to develop, creativity, the accessibility of drug and other medicine, bed room facility, wage and other benefit of employee, training and development, media usage problem, the accessibility of absence of ATM in front of Hospital, shortage of Shop cafeteria and water, sanitary problem, minimize work loading of employee, handling mechanisms of employee and customer success that in order to keep customers satisfaction, infrastructure, shortage of specialist, work strategy for understanding, and supporting his customers to desired business outcomes, and Effective customer success, and requires lack of company-widely changes, and to serve your customers and expand revenue generate, to satisfy his customer to take a dramatic service, to increase his production efficiency, Interfunctional coordination process for the of growth hospital of the public, by Interfunctional coordination, Customers success, Employee Commitment and Organizational Commitment to the validity and confirmation of Significance of Inter-functional Coordination that Affect Organizational Commitment the Mediation Role of Customer Success.

So, in this research that aimed to investigate Factor influencing with the predictive respect to certain indicators to fill those gap and build the role of Inter-functional Coordination on Organizational Commitment to mediate the customer and employee success, in public General Hospital of Bule Hora, Ethiopia.

2. OBJECTIVES OF INVESTIGATION

To analyze the direct effect association among Interfunctional Coordination and Organizational Commitment.

To explain the direct influence association among Interfunctional Coordination and Organizational Commitment.

To determine the relationship association among Customer Success and Organizational Commitment.

3. INTER-FUNCTIONAL COORDINATION

(Sandra L. Fornes, 2020), in the modern business set-up, Interfunctional coordination of employee in governmental organization high value of work activity that stands to be the main point of organizational focus among each organizations, and in that it stands as an additional store, image of organization, attractiveness of working culture, to seek additional revenue generate to each public organization, Motivation of Employee, to search new enterprise to organization and for community by standard, high resources of drug and other benefit to employee and to customer, and among the un-inter-changeable marketing aspects of Interfunctional coordination is a significant business aspect in every organization in that it helps the firm to gather information targeting consumers' needs, and for their competitors, the abilities constantly, and use this information to generate better consumer value repeatedly of the organizations that are the business oriented through inter-functional coordination are highly knowledgeable in relation to the markets in which they operate in and have the capability to utilize the information advantages to make better working value for their target consumers', thus increasing attention in the context of firm performance) (Tschida N., 2017).

In this strategy, the insurance and other fund seeking, and industries in developed economies, such as other western countries, to operate subject to strict regulations, and strong protection from international competition prior, to liberalization, and

the effective implementation of liberalization has sparked stiff competition in the backdrop of an underperforming economy and changes in consumer tastes and preferences, and closer home, the insurance industries of various African countries are experiencing similar challenges, to despite the enhanced growth in premiums from general, and life sectors of the industry, insurance performance in terms of growth in penetration of resource able user to customer activities levels, to share and change new working environment to satisfy his customers and employee of that organization, and profitability continues to be unimpressive, (Lado M., 2016).

4. CUSTOMER SUCCESS

(Lado M., 2016), the delivering customer success kind of loyalty of customer that has highly inspiring value, and experience doesn't happen by accident, and on the beginners guide to lead and show a best direction for the achievement of customer success, Proactive and Reactive Customer success in the organizations pre-emptively, and proactively identify, and address problems that prevent customers from realizing their goals, and they are create real-time visibility into core issues, and coordinate resources to help customers overcome challenges of work behavior.

(Rabinowitz& Hall, 2017), On the other hand, are reactive, putting out fires as they arise to act other tactic that focused on fixing and sure problems in each organization to handle employee and customer success that in order to keep customers satisfied additionally, Customer success on the other hand, is a proactive that implemented that work strategy for understanding, and supporting his customers to desired business outcomes, and Effective customer success, and requires company-wide changes, and to serve your customers. Customer feedback needs to be captured, and disseminated in an inclusive way, and people throughout, the organization need to be empowered to deliver a differentiated, and customized experience that ensures the customer's success no

matter and While a customer success of organizational strategy must be implemented universally, and at a very high organizational top level, tactical application level of the strategy often takes place on a much higher scale of each organizational activity to serve a customer success in organization.

5. ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

(Katzenbach M., 2020), the Performance improvement in an organization goes beyond that has commonly used and serve the accepted principles of good management, and effective and committed leadership by engaging the organizational emotional commitment of the employee Commitment is the differentiating factor between top performing companies, and those of average organizational performance and the emotionality of engaged employees are more productive, and more customer focused based to the, high-levels of employee commitment and organizational commitment that are positively correlated with superior financial performance in organizations to be demonstrated by significant increases in operating, and net profit margin Individuals and teams that are committed to the values, and goals of an organization have a higher morale, and lower turnover, increased job satisfaction, and increased.

6. INVESTIGATION GAP

Usually, following revising diverse publications, it has noted that (Lubbadeh, 2021), The over the many research journal and investigation credentials have the many problems gap in statement of the problem and problem statement to derive time, (Lesener 2019); challenge in the process Inter-functional Coordination and unravel to investigate in in General Hospitals, has to fill the problem gaps of the Significance of Inter-functional Coordination that Affect Organizational Commitment the Mediation Role of Customer Success, and the

association to investigation Inter-functional Coordination predictor in the worth research parameters of technique logical vacuum of theoretical and empirical gap with citation problem and copy pasts in many research paradigms (Strah & Rupp, 2020); like Investigation research approach qualitative, quantitative, and Mixed research design to confirm build the model, Information analyze and Interpretation based on the output of data (Pereira et. al., 2021) , Sampling technique strategy for population category of homogeneity and heterogeneity was face challenge to give good reason for sample size determination for large data sample size fill small sample size in study time, deficit of methodological philosophy gap based on the theory or research approach, and to analyze and interpreted each problem, (Guthier et. al., 2020; Halcomb wt. al., 2018) and it deficit of Information Source, and Collection Techniques, deficit of data analyze and interpreting ability and finally, defecating factors that affect influencing Inter-functional Coordination and Organizational Commitment and the process Exploratory factor analyze (EFA) predictor investigation not fit Thus, investigation of Inter-functional Coordination, has to put forward to solve these research gaps (Waithanji& Wakaba, 2014) .Thus, study will have solved the problem of the Inter-functional Coordination to rise to fill these gaps.

7. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig -1: Conceptual framework
Source: AMOS Output Conceptual Framework

8. HYPOTHESES

H_{1a}: There is statistically significant effect association among Inter-functional Coordination and Organizational Commitment.

H_{2a}: There is statistically significant influence association among Inter-functional Coordination and Customer Success.

H_{3a}: There is statistically significant relationship association among Customer Success and Organizational Commitment.

8.1 Investigation technology

The study shows the Quantitative research paradigms, and it is predicted, and data Explain with Confirmatory factor research design and the investigation will be designed by Confirmatory factor analyze predictor Model fit indexes, to measure Validate Convergent validity of AVE, with internal consistency of Discriminate reliability of Composite reliability, Correlation Matrix, Regression weight Model in Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), (Creswell 2003, cited in Isaq, 2019). Therefore, in the investigation, the study will be designed Confirmatory factor analyses to develop the model investigation design and predictor investigation has to be employed to confirm the model characteristics of the phenomena.

8.2 Sampling Technique

Simple random sample for each member of population of the General Hospital to use sample from Employee of Hospital, and Customer of hospital has an equal chance of assortment and the ways that each workers of General Hospital Employees and Customer that used that Bule Hora General Hospital where has the chance be selected and Stratified random sample: (Yaqub, M, Sahil, F., Shabr, J., and Sohail, M.U., 2022). So, the Employee and Customer participated to collect data for the validation of this study.

Suppose we want to calculate a sample size of a large population whose degree of variability is not known. Assuming the maximum variability, N-total population number, which is equal to 50% (p =0.5) and taking 95% confidence level with ±5% precision,

the calculation for required sample size will be at infinite or 'N' unknown (Kothari, 2004) formula to developed and calculated a representative developed sample for proportions (Cochrane, 2013).

Where, no is the sample size, z is the selected critical value of desired confidence level, p is the estimated proportion of an attribute that is present in the population, q = 1- p and e is the desired level of precision.

p = 0.5 and hence q =1-0.5 = 0.5; e = 0.05; z =1.96

$$n = \frac{z^2pq}{1 + N(e)^2} \quad n = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.5)(0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = 384$$

8.3 Validity and Reliability

Test The research instrument designed in this study – before being distributed to 20 respondents was first tested for the validity and appropriateness of each statement item made in the instrument. For this reason, at this stage, pilot test questionnaires were distributed to 20 respondents, in this case, General Hospital Employees and Customer that used that Bule Hora General Hospital the results of the validity and reliability test of the research instruments in this study obtained that the entire statement items were valid and reliable to be used for the next test.

9. CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSES (CFA) MEASUREMENT MODEL

Fig-2:Confirmatory Factor analysis Measurement Model
Source: Confirmatory factor analysis (2022)

10. COVARIANCE MATRIX

Table -1: Covariance Matrix results

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Conclusions
CUSTS	<-->	ORGCOM	.369	.054	6.900	***	Accepted
INFUC	<-->	CUSTS	.533	.072	7.399	***	Accepted
INFUC	<-->	ORGCOM	.286	.045	6.374	***	Accepted

Source: Covariance Output results 2022

10.1 Model Fit Summary

Covariance matrix a square matrix that displays the variance matrix exhibited by elements of datasets and the covariance Organizational Commitment with Customer success value results 6.900 from Customer success to Interfunctional Coordination result shows the C.R value is 7.399, Organizational Commitment with Interfunctional Coordination C.R Value 6.374 and the pair Covariance error relationship of datasets with Significance p-value 0.000 and the Variance measurement model is a measure of dispersion and can be spread of data from the mean of the given dataset and Covariance matrix is calculated between two variables and is used to measure how the two variables vary together is accepted and the measurement model design is fitted.

11. CORRELATION MATRIX

Table -2: Correlations: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	Conclusions
CUSTS	<-->	INFUC	1.028	Rejected
INFUC	<-->	ORGCOM	.613	Supported
CUSTS	<-->	ORGCOM	.741	Supported

Source: Correlation analyses Matrix 2022

The correlation between the constructed and demonstrated on AMOS static suggested all are meaning full and summarized these number shows the Correlation between the among confirmatory factors analysis in respects to their standard deviation to the study, and the correlation among those factors which helps in confirming measurement model, those the value of Correlation Coefficient value result of all three model has the result more than 0.3 and high and strong correlation coefficient value more than 0.5 and the Alternative Hypothesis has to be Accepted and highly correlated and the Null hypothesis measurement model has to be predicted Rejected or Unsupported based on this reason the Model are highly fitted.

Table -3: Model Fit indices for structural model

NO	Index	Criterion	Final over all model
01	Chi-square χ^2	Low	1.735
02	Df	< 3	.177
03	(P- value)	$\leq$.05	.000
04	Normed chi-square	< 20	307.057
05	Goodness of fit index (GFI)	> .90	.931
06	Adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI)	> .90	.901
07	Normed fit index (NFI)	> .90	.908
08	Relative fit index(RFI)	< .90	.880
09	Incremental fit index (IFI)	>.90	.959
10	Tucker kiwis index (TLI)	>.95	.945
11	Comparative fit index (CFI)	>.95	.958
12	Root Mean Square error (RMR)	$\leq$.05	.081
13	Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	$\leq$.05	.045

Source: Composite Reliability, 2022

The Model Fit Summary Value showed, Chi-square (Chi-square χ^2) direct effect the result to 1.735, Df (Degree of Freedom) result shows .177 will Normed chi-square value 357.057 with a significant P-value is .000, and a CFI value of .958 as (RMR) value has value.081, GFI Results .931, AGFI value results .901, NFI value result .908, Relative fit index(RFI) result .880 along with the (RMSEA) value of .045 and Exogenous variable Interfunctional Coordination, Confounding or Mediating variable of Customer Success and Organizational commitment result, it which implies that the null H0 hypothesis based on the science

estimation is rejected, as well the alternative Ha1 is highly accepted (Hair et al, 2010).

12.DISCRIMINATE RELIABILITY AND CONVERGENT VALIDITY TESTS

Table-4:Standardized Regression Weights: Cronbach Alpha, Composite reliability, and Convergent reliability test results

Indicator variable	Loading		Latent Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE%
CUSS1	.567	<---	Customer Success	.787	.790	.620
CUSS2	.613	<---				
CUSS3	.639	<---				
CUSS4	.735	<---				
CUSS5	.716	<---				
CUSS6	.631	<---				
IFUCO1	.587	<---	Interfunctional Coordination	.860	.826	.610
IFUCO2	.539	<---				
IFUCO3	.592	<---				
IFUCO4	.644	<---				
IFUCO5	.645	<---				
IFUCO6	.581	<---				
ORGC1	.604	<---	Organizational Commitment	.820	.813	.622
ORGC2	.712	<---				
ORGC3	.757	<---				
ORGC4	.781	<---				
ORGC5	.732	<---				
ORGC6	.564	<---				
ORGC7	.693	<---				
ORGC8	.622	<---				
ORGC9	.624	<---				
ORGC10	.721	<---				

Source: Cronbach Alpha, Composite Reliability and AVE result 2022

The Internal Consistency of Discriminate Reliability (Composite Reliability), Cronbach alpha value and Convergent validity is obtained when the AVE% value is greater than 0.5% (Hair et al., 2010), and the AVE% results of convergent validity to constructs of Interfunctional Coordination results model is in AVE>740, it indicate that the Construct Validity test is satisfied, and Composite Reliability tests are more than >0.6% are also accepted when internal reliability of composite reliability it means Interfunctional Coordination value result is .790 Customer success result .826 and Organizational Commitment result .813 and all Cronbach alpha value are > 0.7% it implies result of CR (composite

reliability) is accepted when all constructs show a CR value greater than 0.60, Average extracted variance all (AVE) result has also >0.5% has to be accepted and Cronbach alpha value are > 0.7% because all sub-constructs showed the results of confirmatory factor analysis of value fit indices result is highly accepted and supported (Zainuddin, 2022).

13. STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING (ESM)

In this procedure again model fits would be testified, but the effect among the construct has to be considered for making the different between confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling based on the SEM model demonstrated the Central and non-central indices based the regression weight and the model to be tasted is represented in figure 6.

Fig-3:The overall Structural Equation Modeling Interfunctional Coordination and Organizational Commitment

Source: Results of Structural Equation Modeling Direct hypotheses (2022).

Table-5:Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
CUSTS	<---	INFUC	1.059	.126	8.400	***	Accepted
ORGC0M	<---	INFUC	1.890	.692	4.731	***	Accepted
ORGC0M	<---	CUSTS	1.218	.631	1.930	.054	Rejected
CUSS1	<---	CUSTS	1.000				Accepted
CUSS2	<---	CUSTS	1.010	.092	11.000	***	Accepted
CUSS3	<---	CUSTS	.510	.088	5.775	***	Accepted
CUSS4	<---	CUSTS	.515	.090	5.718	***	Accepted
CUSS5	<---	CUSTS	.500	.092	5.442	***	Accepted
CUSS6	<---	CUSTS	.709	.100	7.073	***	Accepted
IFUC01	<---	INFUC	1.000				Accepted
IFUC02	<---	INFUC	.918	.093	9.896	***	Accepted
IFUC03	<---	INFUC	1.033	.119	8.671	***	Accepted
IFUC04	<---	INFUC	1.026	.113	9.051	***	Accepted
IFUC05	<---	INFUC	1.044	.115	9.090	***	Accepted
IFUC06	<---	INFUC	.629	.107	5.860	***	Accepted
ORGC1	<---	ORGC0M	1.000				Accepted
ORGC2	<---	ORGC0M	1.307	.122	10.748	***	Accepted
ORGC3	<---	ORGC0M	1.307	.117	11.199	***	Accepted
ORGC4	<---	ORGC0M	1.413	.124	11.424	***	Accepted
ORGC5	<---	ORGC0M	1.357	.124	10.952	***	Accepted
ORGC6	<---	ORGC0M	1.119	.124	9.018	***	Accepted
ORGC7	<---	ORGC0M	.770	.116	6.619	***	Accepted
ORGC8	<---	ORGC0M	-.040	.101	-.397	.691	Rejected
ORGC9	<---	ORGC0M	-.042	.097	-.433	.665	Rejected
ORGC10	<---	ORGC0M	.036	.094	.380	.704	Rejected

Source: Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model, 2022).

The Standardized Regression Weights suppose we have a network with a path connecting from latent variable and measurement variables, that means from Measurement model and structural model value of standardized path coefficient beta is highly affected, and it can be expected to increase by one standardized deviation(error) that means that predicted variables from its own mean while holding, all the other relevant variables is constant and Interfunctional coordination, Customer success, Organizational Commitment value that indicted variables has goes up by 1 standard deviation that goes more the measurement model output except, Organizational Commitment Question 8, 9 and 10 all measurement model output result standard deviations and the Standardized coefficient has to be less than 0.05% based on this assumptions the model value of regression weight is very well and the standardize regression weight group results have highly affected and solve the problem in General Hospital of Bule Hora.

14. HYPOTHESES TEST RESULTS

Table-6:Standard Regression Weights hypothesis

No	Indigenous Variable	Exogenous Variables	Estimate	C. E	C.R	P	Conclusion
CUSTS	<---	INFUC	1.059	.126	8.400	***	Accepted
ORGC0M	<---	INFUC	1.890	.692	4.731	***	Accepted
ORGC0M	<---	CUSTS	1.218	.631	1.930	.054	Rejected

Source: Output of Hypothesis testing 2022.

Hypothesis testing is done with (Interfunctional coordination with Customer Success C.R Value 8.400, Interfunctional coordination with Organizational Commitments' value 4.731, and Customer success with Organizational Commitment value 1. 930, with three hypothesis result less than the 0.05 using the t-count that estimate by SEM in AMOS V. 23 software, the t-count is the critical ratio (CR) value for weight regression, and the (CR), the value is greater than 1.967 that means (Interfunctional coordination or the likelihood with all P–value result is < 0.05, then H0 Null hypothesis can be rejected, and the alternative p– value estimation can be Accepted < 0.05,the output of Customer Success with Organizational Commitment result shows 0.054 that means the alternative hypothesis is rejected and Null Hypothesis are accepted and the remaining two are highly accepted.

15. STANDARDIZED REGRESSION WEIGHTS

Table-7:Standardized Regression Weights

			Estimate
CUSTS	<---	INFUC	1.028
ORGC10	<---	INFUC	2.090
ORGC10	<---	CUSTS	1.387
CUSS1	<---	CUSTS	.567
CUSS2	<---	CUSTS	.613
CUSS3	<---	CUSTS	.639
CUSS4	<---	CUSTS	.735
CUSS5	<---	CUSTS	.716
CUSS6	<---	CUSTS	.631
IFUCO1	<---	INFUC	.587
IFUCO2	<---	INFUC	.539
IFUCO3	<---	INFUC	.592
IFUCO4	<---	INFUC	.644
IFUCO5	<---	INFUC	.645
IFUCO6	<---	INFUC	.581
ORGC1	<---	ORGC10	.604
ORGC2	<---	ORGC10	.712
ORGC3	<---	ORGC10	.757
ORGC4	<---	ORGC10	.781
ORGC5	<---	ORGC10	.732
ORGC6	<---	ORGC10	.564
ORGC7	<---	ORGC10	.693
ORGC8	<---	ORGC10	.622
ORGC9	<---	ORGC10	.624
ORGC10	<---	ORGC10	.721

Source: Standardized Regression Weights 2022

There are effect of regression coefficients suppose we have a network with a path connecting from latent variable and measurement variables to the manifest variables the standardized path coefficient of regression weight, is highly affected that would be expected to increase by one standardized deviation from its mean to other predicted variables from its own mean while holding all other relevant variables is constant and when Inter-functional coordination, Customer success, and Organizational Commitment and other indicted variables has goes up by 1 standard deviation, and goes up by More than 0.5, and the Standardized regressions coefficient value of the model is very well, and the

standardize regression weight group results have highly affected and solve the problem of public Bule Hora General Hospital .

16. STANDARDIZE TOTAL EFFECT VALUE

Table-8:Standardized Total Effects

	ORGC10	INFUC	CUSTS
ORGC10	.022	.000	.000
ORGC9	-.027	.000	.000
ORGC8	-.025	.000	.000
ORGC7	.384	.000	.000
ORGC6	.551	.000	.000
ORGC5	.732	.000	.000
ORGC4	.779	.000	.000
ORGC3	.757	.000	.000
ORGC2	.714	.000	.000
ORGC1	.644	.000	.000
IFUCO6	.000	.412	.000
IFUCO5	.000	.658	.000
IFUCO4	.000	.652	.000
IFUCO3	.000	.590	.000
IFUCO2	.000	.523	.000
IFUCO1	.000	.577	.000
CUSS6	.000	.000	.478
CUSS5	.000	.000	.314
CUSS4	.000	.000	.350
CUSS3	.000	.000	.354
CUSS2	.000	.000	.605
CUSS1	.000	.000	.528

Source: Standardized Total Effects Source 2022.

The total (direct and indirect) effect of Interfunctional Coordination with Organizational Commitment with mediating role of Customer success with the overall total direct and indirect effect group results have highly affected and significantly fit to solve the problem of public Bule

Hora General Hospital based on the observation output results.

17. CONCLUSIONS

Covariance matrix a square matrix that displays the variance matrix exhibited by elements of datasets and the covariance Organizational Commitment with Customer success value results 6.900 from Customer success to Interfunctional Coordination result shows the C.R value is 7.399, Organizational Commitment with Interfunctional Coordination C.R Value 6.374 and the pair Covariance error relationship of datasets with Significance p-value 0.000 and the Variance measurement model is a measure of dispersion and can be spread of data from the mean of the given dataset and Covariance matrix is calculated between two variables and is used to measure how the two variables vary together is accepted and the measurement model design is fitted.

The correlation between the constructed and demonstrated on AMOS static suggested all are meaning full and summarized these number shows the Correlation between the among confirmatory factors analysis in respects to their standard deviation to the study, and the correlation among those factors which helps in confirming measurement model, those the value of Correlation Coefficient value result of all three model has the result more than 0.3 and high and strong correlation coefficient value more than 0.5 and the Alternative Hypothesis has to be Accepted and highly correlated and the Null hypothesis measurement model has to be predicted Rejected or Unsupported based on this reseon the Model are highly fitted.

The Internal Consistency of Discriminate Reliability (Composite Reliability), Cronbach alpha value and Convergent validity is obtained when the AVE% value is greater than 0.5% (Hair et al., 2010), and the AVE% results of convergent validity to constructs of Interfunctional Coordination results model is in AVE >740, it indicate that the Construct Validity test is satisfied, and Composite Reliability tests are more

than >0.6% are also accepted when internal reliability of composite reliability it means Interfunctional Coordination value result is .790 Customer success result .826 and Organizational Commitment result .813 and all Cronbach alpha value are > 0.7% it implies result of CR (composite reliability) is accepted when all constructs show a CR value greater than 0.60, Average extracted variance all (AVE) result has also >0.5% has to be accepted and Cronbach alpha value are > 0.7% because all sub-constructs showed the results of confirmatory factor analysis of value fit indices result is highly accepted and supported (Zainuddin, 2022).

The Standardized Regression Weights suppose we have a network with a path connecting from latent variable and measurement variables, that means from Measurement model and structural model value of standardized path coefficient beta is highly affected, and it can be expected to increase by one standardized deviation(error) that means that predicted variables from its own mean while holding, all the other relevant variables is constant and Interfunctional coordination, Customer success, Organizational Commitment value that indicted variables has goes up by 1 standard deviation that goes more the measurement model output except, Organizational Commitment Question 8, 9 and 10 all measurement model output result standard deviations and the Standardized coefficient has to be less than < 0.05% based on this assumptions the model value of regression weight is very well and the standardize regression weight group results have highly affected and solve the problem in General Hospital of Bule Hora.

Hypothesis testing is done with (Interfunctional coordination with Customer Success C.R Value 8.400, Interfunctional coordination with Organizational Commitments' value 4.731, and Customer success with Organizational Commitment value 1. 930, with three hypothesis result less than the 0.05 using the t-count that estimate by SEM in AMOS V. 23 software, the t-count is the critical ratio (CR) value for weight regression, and the (CR), the

value is greater than 1.967 that means (Interfunctional coordination or the likelihood with all P–value result is < 0.05 , then H_0 Null hypothesis can be rejected, and the alternative p– value estimation can be Accepted < 0.05 , the output of Customer Success with Organizational Commitment result shows 0.054 that means the alternative hypothesis is rejected and Null Hypothesis are accepted and the remaining two are highly accepted.

There are effect of regression coefficients suppose we have a network with a path connecting from latent variable and measurement variables to the manifest variables the standardized path coefficient of regression weight, is highly affected that would be expected to increase by one standardized deviation from its mean to other predicted variables from its own mean while holding all other relevant variables is constant and when Inter–functional coordination, Customer success, and Organizational Commitment and other indicted variables has goes up by 1 standard deviation, and goes up by More than 0.5, and the Standardized regressions coefficient value of the model is very well, and the standardize regression weight group results have highly affected and solve the problem of public Bule Hora General Hospital.

The total (direct and indirect) effect of Interfunctional Coordination with Organizational Commitment with mediating role of Customer success with the overall total direct and indirect effect group results have highly affected and significantly fit to solve the problem of public Bule Hora General Hospital based on the observation output results.

REFERENCES

- [1] Altinay Dart & Aglonye M. (2016). the employee and Organizational commitment in the workplace to develop a framework. *International journal of Logistic and Supply chain management* , 123–145.
- [2] Birhanu et.al. (2017). Interfunctional Coordination and Organizational Commitment on the economic growth of the Ethiopian . *International journal of Multidisciplinary research* , 234–250.
- [3] Creswell 2003, cited in Isaq. (2019). SEM analyze of to measure structural model to design Regression model of Standard Regression Weights to measure direct and indirect effect, Correlation and hypostasized direct and indirect effect to investigate the research. *International Journal of Business and Social science* , 238–270.
- [4] Gada Gizachew W. (2021). the role Competitor orientation and Customer Orientation have on Enterprnioure marketing Efficiency . *International journal of multi deciplinary research* , 1–10.
- [5] Hair et al. (2010). Index category and accepted value of model fit indexed. *International journal business and social research* , 554–582.
- [6] Karmani, N. Y. (2020). comfirmatory factor analyses teacher leadership measurement model. *International journal of Business and Social science* , 697–706.
- [7] Katzenbach M. (2020). The Performance improvement in an organization goes beyond that has commonly used and serve the accepted principles of good management, and effective and committed leadership . *International Journal of Human resource Management and Leadreship* , 345–361.
- [8] Dr. A. Shaji George, & A.S. Hovan George. (2022). Data Sharing Made Easy by Technology Trends: New Data Sharing and Privacy Preserving Technologies that Bring in a New Era of Data Monetization. *Partners Universal International Research Journal (PUIRJ)*, 01(03), 13–19.
- [9] Lado M. (2016). the beginners guide to lead and show a best direction for the achievement of customer success, Proactive and Reactive Customer success. *International Journal of management and Leadership* , 360–378.
- [10] Lado M. (2016). the insurance industries of various African countries are experiencing similar challenges, to despite the enhanced growth in premiums from general. *International journal of Business and Leadership* , 345–360.
- [11] Lubbadeh. (2021). the diverse investigations have been completed on the topic of Marketing orientation. *Tradintional Management Journal and Sustainability*, 160–167.
- [12] Malgharn et, al. (2019). the benefits of an organization to coordinated, and at an internal capacity of firms or organization profitability. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance* , 234–251.
- [13] Mukulu & Kahiri. (2017). the contribution of Organization activities, and it has mostly been conceptualized on the basis of financial measures. *Traditional Journal of Law and Social Science* , 345–360.

- [14]Pereira et. al.,. (2021). Investigation research approach quantitative, quantitative and mixed, to research design to confirm build the model, Information analyze and Interpretation based on the output of data . Journal of Marketing and Management , 322-256.
- [15]Rabinowitz& Hall. (2017). the organization need to be empowered to deliver a differentiated, and customized experience that ensures the customer's success . International journal of Leadership and management , 345-367.
- [16]Sandra L. Fornes. (2020). the major enabler of organizational performance for best Interfunctional commitment, the growth of each organization from medium to general, and the expansion of branch. Journal of Interpriniour ship and Innovation , 345-360.
- [17]Swiss R. (2018). the contribution of total insurance premiums of every organization, is focused on its organizational performance thoroughly which it assures on its organizational sustainability and rapid growth change. International Journal of Multi Deciplinary Research , 160-182.
- [18]Tschida N. (2017). the business oriented through inter-functional coordination are highly knowledgeable in relation to the markets in which they operate in and have the capability to utilize the information advantages . International Journal of Accounting and Finance , 167-182.
- [19]Zainuddin, K. a. (2022). Research needs to obtain the realibility measerement model obtain chrobich alpha Cr and AVE. International journal of Logistics and Supply chain Manegenent , 667-707.